

**СПЕЦИФИКА БЕЗЭКВИВАЛЕНТНОСТИ
В ЛЕКСИЧЕСКОЙ СИСТЕМЕ РУССКОГО И АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКОВ /
THE SPECIFICS OF NON-EQUIVALENCE IN THE LEXICAL SYSTEM
OF RUSSIAN AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES**

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The relevance of the study lies in the growing interest in exploring foreign-language cultures, driven by the strengthening of international contacts. The aim of the research is to identify the most effective strategies for translating non-equivalent vocabulary between English and Russian. The concepts of "non-equivalent vocabulary", "realia", "lacuna" are defined; the methods of conveying the semantics of non-equivalent vocabulary in translation are described. The types of interlingual lexical non-equivalence are analyzed. The paper concludes that explication is the most effective method of conveying the semantics of non-equivalent vocabulary into English.